

A novel samarium(III) nanocomposite carbon paste electrode based on *N,N'*-bis(8-quinoly)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide as a selectophore

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Manuscript received online 28 January 2017, accepted 09 February 2017

Abstract : A sufficient amounts of *N,N'*-bis(8-quinoly)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide (QPC) was applied as a new ionophore for fabrication of new nanocomposite carbon paste electrode (CPE) modified with nanosilica/MWCNT. The electrochemical behavior of the new prepared CPE was investigated in the presence of various metal ions. The best composition of ingredients was achieved in optimization stage for QPC : 2%, binder (paraffin oil) : 25%, modifier (MWCNT : 1%, NS : 0.1%), and graphite powder : 71.9%. This new CPE displayed a Nernstian response by the slope of 19.7 ± 0.9 mV decade⁻¹ in the linear range of 1.0×10^{-8} – 1.0×10^{-3} mole L⁻¹ with a lower detection limit of 9.0×10^{-9} mole L⁻¹ toward Sm³⁺ ion. The pH range of this new samarium(III) electrode was gained 3.7 to 7.3 with a response time about 13 s. The matched potential method was applied to study the selectivity of Sm³⁺CPE in comparison with many common cations which showed the negligible disturbance of all other cations on the proposed samarium(III) electrode. It was successfully used as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of Sm³⁺ ions with EDTA and determination of Sm³⁺ content in several blends of ions.

Keywords : Nanocomposite, carbon paste electrode, samarium(III), ion selective electrode, *N,N'*-bis(8-quinoly)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide, potentiometry, sensor.

Introduction

Rare-earth elements have been found numerous applications in many industries. Although they are classified in one group but each of the member has different properties and usage. They are used increasingly as major components in laser, phosphors, magnetic bubble memory films, refractive index lenses, fiber optics and superconductors. Among the lanthanide series samarium is the sixth element with atomic number 62. Samarium as like as other rare earth elements has several implementations in various fields such as use as an appropriate absorber in industry and in CaF₂ crystals as a doping element in order to manufacture of optical masers and lasers, and so on; which cause to augment the concentrations of Sm³⁺ in humans body,

animals and soil particles^{1,2}.

Growing various lanthanide applications causes their selective determinations become important². Among several time consuming and costly instrumental methods which have been used for determination of the samarium ion in aqueous solutions³⁻⁸ potentiometric techniques based on ion selective carbon paste electrodes (CPEs) with some advantages such as renewable surface, stable response, and low Ohmic resistance can be regularly used as acceptable analytical method⁹⁻¹¹. Also, the potentiometric electrodes in comparison with advanced analytical instruments offer a portable and nondestructive method for selective analysis of ionic and total amount of a species in a wide concentration linear range.

Lately, some ISEs for lanthanide ions including samarium were reported by us and other researchers¹²⁻⁵⁸.

In the present work, a new nanocomposite Sm^{3+} CPE was introduced. In this CPE, *N,N'*-bis(8-quinoly)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide (QPC) (Fig. 1) was applied as the lipophilic selective element. The proposed electrode has been successfully used for the selective monitoring of Sm^{3+} ion.

Fig. 1. Structure of QPC.

Experimental

EMF measurements :

All measurements were carried out with Sm^{3+} CPE in accordance to the following cell assembly by put to use a potentiometric cell involving the Sm^{3+} CPE as indicating electrode, an Ag/AgCl electrode purchased from Azar electrode, Iran co. as a reference electrode that was linked to a potentiometer, a Corning ion analyzer with a 250 pH/mV meter for the potential measurements, at room temperature (25.0 °C).

The activities would be calculated by Debye-Hückel procedure that is given as⁵⁹ :

$$\log \gamma = -0.511z^2 \left[\frac{\mu^{1/2}}{1 + 1.5\mu^{1/2}} - 0.2\mu \right]$$

Chemicals and reagents :

Nanosilica (NS), HDK[®] H20 was obtained from Wacker Company (Germany) and Multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with 10–40 nm diameters, 1–25 μm length with 95% purity were purchased from Research Institute of the Petroleum Industry (Iran), Merck Chemical and Aldrich Co. were the suppliers for the nitrate and chloride salts of all cations, *N,N'*-bis(8-quinoly)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide (QPC), high-purity paraffin oil and graphite powder (1–2 μm particle size). Doubly distilled de-ionized water was used throughout.

Carbon paste electrode preparation :

The CPE preparation proceeding was followed by mix the paste composition including paraffin oil (binder), QPC (ionophore), MWCNTs and NS (modifier), and graphite powder (inert matrix) entirely about 30–40 min to get homogenization paste. Next, the final paste was packed up to the tip of a tube containing a wire which played the role as the electrical contact (here copper wire). Then, by the piece of soft paper the surface of CPE was polished to replace the external layer of the carbon paste by the new smoothed one. Finally, the electrode was soaked in a 1.0×10^{-3} mole L^{-1} $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solutions for 48 h.

Results and discussion

Potential response of the electrode :

Among several lanthanide and some of other cations electrodes which was prepared to study the Nernstian response of new designed CPE based on QPC by potentiometric method, according to final results, the Sm^{3+} CPE shows the best Nernstian response (Fig. 2).

Optimization of the Sm^{3+} CPE :

As it is general in preparation of any carbon paste electrodes, the ingredients of the paste should be optimized to achieve a best response. The main selectivity

Fig. 2. Potential responses of various ion-selective electrodes based on CP-QPC.

and response of the electrode towards the Sm^{3+} ion is because of the used ionophore QPC in the paste which can form a complex with samarium ions selectively. The other ingredients are used to slightly optimize the main response and are like and additive. In optimization stage we seek to get the best electrochemical response by changing the type and amount of each ingredient. The final results which are listed in Table 1 show the best response for Sm^{3+} CPE No. 7 with a composition of 0.1% NS, 1% MWCNT, 2% QPC, 25% paraffin oil and 71.9% graphite powder. The ionophore as an active material (here QPC) is one of the main ingredi-

ents of any CPE, so the variety amount of QPC was used to fabricate a series of nanocomposite Sm^{3+} CPEs to test the selectivity of it. Absence of the ligand in the paste (electrode no. 9) causes no significant response. MWCNT as a nanomodifier is another component which causes to improve the behavior of the CPE such as conductivity of the sensor, increases the transduction of the chemical signal to electrical signal, and develops the dynamic working range and so on. As well as two more ingredients of CPE are paraffin oil (binder) and graphite powder as an inert matrix. The other nanomodifier is nanosilica which is a filler compound with high specific surface area that enhances the mechanical properties of CPE and helps to extraction of the ions into the surface of the CPE due to its hydrophobic property.

Calibration curve :

The potential response of the Sm^{3+} CPE based on QPC versus the various activity of Sm^{3+} solution, illustrated in Fig. 3 as a calibration curve which put out the wide linear range from 1.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-3} mole L^{-1} and the slope of 19.7 ± 0.9 mV decade $^{-1}$ with lower detection limit of 9.0×10^{-9} mole L^{-1} of samarium(III) ions concentration⁵⁹⁻⁷³.

Table 1. Optimization of the Sm^{3+} CPE ingredients

Electrode No.	Composition of carbon paste (wt. %)					Slope (mV/decade)	Dynamic linear range (M)
	Binder (Paraffin oil)	Ligand	Graphite powder	MWCNTs	Nano-silicon		
1	25	2	71.7	1	0.3	18.0 ± 0.5	$1.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
2	30	2	67.7	1	0.3	18.3 ± 0.2	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
3	35	2	61.7	1	0.3	16.0 ± 0.4	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
4	25	2	70.7	2	0.3	17.5 ± 0.8	$5.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
5	25	2	69.7	3	0.3	17.0 ± 0.6	$1.0 \times 10^{-7} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
6	25	2	71.5	1	0.5	16.5 ± 0.3	$1.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
7	25	2	71.9	1	0.1	19.7 ± 0.9	$1.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
8	25	1	72.9	1	0.1	17.0 ± 0.6	$5.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$
9	25	0	74.9	1	0.1	No response	-
10	25	3	70.9	1	0.1	19.6 ± 0.9	$1.0 \times 10^{-8} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$

Fig. 3. Calibration curves of the QPC-based Sm^{3+} CP sensor.

Fig. 5. Dynamic response time of Sm^{3+} CPE based on QCP.

Fig. 4. pH effect of 1.0×10^{-3} mole L^{-1} of Sm^{3+} solution on the Sm^{3+} sensor based on QPC.

pH influence :

To study the effect of hydronium ions on the potential response of Sm^{3+} CPE over the pH range from 1.0 to 11.0 the specified concentration of Sm^{3+} solution (1.0×10^{-3} mole L^{-1}) was applied. According to Fig. 4 no consequential change observed on the potential response over pH range of 3.7–7.3. The changes of potential at low pH values are attributed to the electrode response to H_3O^+ ion which is due to the protonation of the ionophore in the paste and the changes of potential at higher pH values is due to the formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Sm^{3+} ions in the solution^{74–80}.

Dynamic response time of the Sm^{3+} CPE :

The response time of new Sm^{3+} CPE was assayed by apply the lower (1.0×10^{-8} mole L^{-1}) to the higher (1.0×10^{-3} mole L^{-1}) concentration of the Sm^{3+} solution, respectively. Conforming to Fig. 5, the response time of Sm^{3+} CPE was ~ 13 s.

Selectivity studies of the Sm^{3+} CPE :

The priority of primary ion over interfering ions in terms of selectivity coefficients was measured graphically by the match potential method (MPM)^{81–84}. According to MPM the potential of the specific activity of Sm^{3+} ions solution was measured, next, the amount of interfering ions solution was sequentially added to the same solution and the potential was read (1×10^{-7} to 1×10^{-3} mol L^{-1}). In the last, the final results getting by the ratio of primary ion (A) (1×10^{-8} mol L^{-1}) activity (concentration due to the low ionic strength) changes to the interfering ion (B) that is given as :

$$K_{ij}^{\text{MPM}} = \frac{\Delta a_A}{a_R}$$

In accordance of Table 2 an acceptable performance of the designed CPE toward the Sm^{3+} ions was observed which indicates the specific interaction between

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients ($K_{Sm^{2+}}^{MPM}$) of proposed

Sm ³⁺ sensor			
Interfering ion	$K_{Sm,B}^{MPM}$	Interfering ion	$K_{Sm,B}^{MPM}$
Pr ³⁺	6.1×10^{-4}	Al ³⁺	1.0×10^{-5}
La ³⁺	5.6×10^{-4}	Cr ³⁺	3.6×10^{-5}
Tm ³⁺	7.1×10^{-4}	Fe ³⁺	3.5×10^{-3}
Nd ³⁺	7.7×10^{-4}	Mg ²⁺	7.9×10^{-5}
Eu ³⁺	5.6×10^{-5}	Pb ²⁺	6.4×10^{-5}
Ho ³⁺	4.1×10^{-5}	Co ²⁺	2.8×10^{-4}
Gd ³⁺	2.5×10^{-5}	Cd ²⁺	7.9×10^{-4}
Yb ³⁺	2.1×10^{-4}	Ca ²⁺	9.0×10^{-5}
Er ³⁺	7.8×10^{-5}	Ni ²⁺	2.1×10^{-5}
Tb ³⁺	6.6×10^{-5}	Na ⁺	6.9×10^{-5}
Dy ³⁺	6.1×10^{-4}	K ⁺	7.4×10^{-5}

Sm³⁺ ions and QPC in comparison with other cations.

Analytical application :

In order to do potentiometric titration 25 ml of 1.0×10^{-4} mole L⁻¹ Sm³⁺ was titrated by the certain amounts of 1.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ EDTA via the Sm³⁺CPE as an indicator electrode. According to Fig. 6, this electrode can successfully determine the amount of Sm³⁺ ions in solution.

As well as this new prepared Sm³⁺CPE could put to use for scanning low level concentrations of

Fig. 6. Titration curves of Sm³⁺ solution (25 mL 1.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹) with EDTA (1.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹).

samarium(III) ion in the mixtures containing various cations. According to Table 3 the accuracy of the Sm³⁺ ions detection in different solutions of different metal ions is almost quantitative is clear.

Conclusion

Due to trend of *N,N'*-bis(8-quinolyl)pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide (QPC) to form complex with Sm³⁺ ions, it was used as a sensing material in create of new Sm³⁺CPE. According to optimization stage, the best composition for the Sm³⁺CPE with nearest Nernstian behavior (slope of 19.7 ± 0.9 mV per decade over the

Table 3. Determination of Sm³⁺ ion in the presence of metal ions mixtures

Sm ³⁺ (mol L ⁻¹)	Added cations (mol L ⁻¹)	Found ^a (mol L ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Gd(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Pr(NO ₃) ₃	0.98×10^{-8}	98
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Eu(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Er(NO ₃) ₃	0.99×10^{-8}	99
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)La(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Ho(NO ₃) ₃	1.02×10^{-8}	102
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Dy(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Yb(NO ₃) ₃	1.04×10^{-8}	104
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Tb(NO ₃) ₃ and (0.00001)Nd(NO ₃) ₃	0.97×10^{-8}	97
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Na(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.99×10^{-8}	99
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Pb(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)Ni(NO ₃) ₂	1.00×10^{-8}	100
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Co(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)Al(NO ₃) ₃	1.01×10^{-8}	101
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)K(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Mg(NO ₃) ₂	1.03×10^{-8}	103
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Pb(NO ₃) ₂ , (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂ and (0.00001)K(NO ₃)	0.97×10^{-8}	97
1.0×10^{-8}	(0.00001)Al(NO ₃) ₃ , (0.00001)Na(NO ₃) and (0.00001)Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.98×10^{-8}	98

^aResults are based on three measurements.

wide linear range of 1.0×10^{-8} – 1.0×10^{-3} mole L⁻¹ and the detection limit of 9.0×10^{-9} mole L⁻¹ in the pH range of 3.7–7.3) was belonged to QPC : 2%, paraffin oil : 25%, MWCNT : 1%, NS : 0.1%, and graphite powder : 71.9%.

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